

The Role of Thermal Density Currents in the Generation of Planetary Magnetic Fields

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Abstract

In this study, we propose a conjecture regarding generating magnetic fields in the interior of planets. Specifically, we investigate the potential contribution of a thermal density current, which is generated by the Seebeck effect, to the intensity of the planetary magnetic field. Our analysis reveals that the scale of the magnetic field associated with the thermal density current is of comparable magnitude to the observed magnetic fields on planets within our solar system. To assess this hypothesis, we leverage degenerate Fermi gas approximation for the fluid internal cores of the planets, enabling us to evaluate the magnitude of thermal contribution to the planetary magnetic field for Mercury, Earth, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. Finally, we validate our results by comparing them with the magnetic fields measured by several spatial missions. We will not solve the magnetohydrodynamic equations; instead, our discussion will focus on the order of magnitude of the magnetic field and its associated physics. At this level, we will not consider the specific mechanisms, such as dynamo conversion, responsible for generating the observable magnetic field. Our goal is to provide a scaling that aligns with astronomical observations.

1 Keywords:

planetary magnetic field, thermomagnetic model, Seebeck effect, planetology of fluid planets, Earth's interior structure and properties

2 Introduction

Generating magnetic fields from moving electromagnetic systems has been a long-standing and intriguing problem in the scientific community. Researchers have devoted considerable efforts to understanding the phenomenon of magnetic field generation through various mechanisms, including the dynamics of

deforming solid bodies and fluid flows. Celestial bodies within our solar system, including the Sun, planets, and their satellites, have been found to exhibit magnetic fields [1, 2].

In recent times, spatial missions such as MESSENGER, Juno, and Cassini have played a crucial role in expanding our knowledge of planetary interiors that are associated with the planet's magnetic fields[3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. The data collected from these missions have been pivotal in developing models and simulations to better comprehend the underlying processes responsible for generating and sustaining magnetic fields in these diverse systems.

In this Brief Research Report, we are not solving the magnetohydrodynamic equations. Rather, the primary objective of our study is to propose a scaling model for the magnetic fields generated by planets and their satellites, aiming to capture at least partially, if not entirely, the magnitude of the planetary magnetic field. Over the years, several scaling approaches have been developed, each tailored to address certain aspects of the complex interplay between fluid dynamics and magnetic fields. One widely used scaling approach involves the Elsasser number units, given by $B \sim \sqrt{\rho\Omega/\sigma}$, where Ω denotes the rotational velocity of the planet or satellite, ρ signifies the fluid density, and σ is the electrical conductivity of the medium. In addition to the Elsasser number scaling, another significant scaling model derived from an exact solution in cylindrical geometry has proven to be insightful for certain scenarios. In this model, the magnetic scaling is given by $B \sim \Omega R\sqrt{\rho\mu_0}$, where μ_0 represents the magnetic permeability of the vacuum and R stands for the radius of the cylinder [18]. An exhaustive discussion about the scaling laws for planetary dynamos can be found in Refs. [19, 20] and in Ref. [21] for the estimation of the magnetic field evolution on giant extra-solar planets and brown dwarfs. Furthermore, in Ref. [20], Christensen introduces a temperature scaling and indicates the need to know the convected heat flux in the dynamo. In Ref.[22], the authors showed that the contribution due to a thermal density current (Seebeck effect), $\mathbf{J}_T = -\sigma\alpha(T)\nabla T$, may take care of a part or completely of the planetary magnetic field, applying the new approach to Earth, Jupiter, and Ganymede, Jupiter's satellite. The inclusion of the thermal current is important as it considers the influence of temperature and the statistical properties of the conducting fluid within the planet.

As we will see, the degenerate Fermi's gas approximation, i.e., when the Fermi energy exceeds by far $k_B T$, provides a well-founded hypothesis for the behavior of the conducting fluid within the planet, and we will apply this approach to Mercury, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. With the exclusion of Mars, with its considered fossil magnetic field, and Venus, where accepted models are lacking and the magnetic field strength is extremely small or nonexistent, we will obtain a sufficiently accurate scaling of the planetary magnetic fields. According to our conjecture, quantum mechanics should be involved in evaluating the planetary magnetic fields.

3 Theory: Thermal contribution to the magnetic field

As the introduction states, we aim to provide a scaling for the magnetic field associated with a non-uniform temperature. This condition is very typical in the interiors of stars and planets, which are described by the magneto-hydrodynamics equations. The foundation of magnetic fluid dynamics can be found in traditional textbooks, such as [23].

Let us consider the current density \mathbf{J} given by the constitutive relation $\mathbf{J} = \sigma(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})$, i.e. Ohm's law, where \mathbf{E} is the electric field, $\mathbf{B} = \mu\mathbf{H}$ the magnetic induction, and σ is the electrical conductivity of the medium.

As pointed out in [22], a non-uniform temperature generates an electrical current proportional to the temperature gradient (Seebeck effect). This is a physical condition that is common in the interiors of most solar system objects. We stress that the fluid velocity is a three-dimensional vector field function of the polar coordinates, and consequently, the gradient of temperature, in general, is not radial. Together with a melted outer core, the thermal density current, $\mathbf{J}_T = -\sigma\alpha(T)\nabla T$, with $\alpha(T)$ the Seebeck coefficient, and T the temperature, gives a contribution to the magnetic field. As already stated, we are unwilling to solve the full magnetohydrodynamic equations. Our discussion will focus on the magnetic field's magnitude order and the associated physics. As we will see, the field scaling associated with the Seebeck effect leads to quantum mechanics considerations. To quantify the above discussion, we can write the total current density as [24]:

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma [\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} - \alpha(T)\nabla T]. \quad (1)$$

As shown in [24], quantum calculations give an exact expression for the Seebeck coefficient $\alpha(T)$. However, for our purposes, it is sufficient to use a rough estimate, i.e.,

$$|\alpha(T)| \sim k_B \frac{k_B T}{e\varepsilon_F}, \quad (2)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, e is the electron charge,

$$\varepsilon_F = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} (3\pi^2 n)^{2/3} \quad (3)$$

is the Fermi energy. The number of electrons per unit volume, n , is related to the mass density ρ of the conducting material by the relationship $\rho = nm_N\mu_N$, where m_N is the nucleon mass and μ_N is the number of nucleons per electron. In general, the Ohmic term may result hard to estimate. We may give an order of magnitude in the case of Earth. In agreement with Christensen [20], we may ignore the electric field and estimate the term $\sigma\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$. Using the Earth data in Ref. [20], i.e. $v \approx 10^{-4}$ m/s and $B \approx 20$ Gauss, we found that $\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}$ is of the same order or higher of $\alpha\nabla T$. This holds in the case of \mathbf{v} perpendicular to \mathbf{B} . But, as pointed out by Christensen [20], \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{B} could be largely aligned with

each other. If this is the case, the ohmic contribution could be negligible. That being said, we focus on the thermal contribution of the current and consequently, the related magnetic field, i.e.,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_T = \mu_0 \mathbf{J}_T = -\mu_0 \sigma \alpha(T) \nabla T \quad (4)$$

where μ_0 is the vacuum permeability and the subscript T stands for thermal. Following [22], and considering the corresponding scale-equation, we may write as magnitude order of the terms of Eq. (4)

$$|\nabla \times \mathbf{B}_T| \sim B_T / \Delta R, \quad |\nabla T| \sim \Delta T / \Delta R, \quad (5)$$

where ΔT is the difference in temperature in the outer core, and ΔR is the size scale of the outer core. Also, with the same degree of approximation from (2) we have

$$\alpha(T) \nabla T \sim \alpha(T_I + \delta T) \nabla T \sim \alpha(T_I) \nabla T \sim k_B \frac{k_B T_I}{e \varepsilon_F} \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta R}, \quad (6)$$

where T_I is the temperature at the beginning of the outer core (see Fig. 1). Then, plugging Eqs. (5), (6) into Eq. (4), we obtain the scale strength of the thermal contribution to the magnetic field

$$B_T = \mu_0 \sigma \frac{k_B T_I}{e \varepsilon_F} k_B \Delta T. \quad (7)$$

4 Results and Discussion

We will now apply the theory developed in the previous section to the interiors of the planets in the solar system, except for Mars, which has a fossil magnetic field, and Venus, where accepted models are lacking, and the magnetic field strength is extremely small or nonexistent. We will evaluate the contribution to the magnetic fields of the planets with a conducting melted outer core, considering it as a degenerate Fermi gas in its electronic component. As we will see, the internal temperature of the planets and their satellites, and more in general of the other solar system objects, is clearly below Fermi's temperature, $T_F = \varepsilon_F / k_B$, justifying the approximation.

The layer structure is common to all planets in our solar system, regardless of the component material of the several melted layers, metallic-ferrous in the case of rocky planets, and liquids with high conductivity in the case of giant planets (see Figure 1). Their fluid dynamics is likely a three-dimensional flow, as in the Earth case, where the inner core spins faster than the rest of the planet [25], generating a three-dimensional velocity field. In Ref. [22], the strength of the thermal contribution to the magnetic field was evaluated for Earth, Jupiter, and Ganymede, giving the order of magnitude of the observed values of the respective magnetic field at the surface.

We start the new discussion with Mercury, which has been explored in recent years by several space missions, particularly by the MESSENGER spacecraft

that orbited Mercury for more than four years. Mercury has a radius of $R_P = 2440$ Km, an inner core radius $R_I \sim 1000$ Km, an outer core radius $R_O \sim 2000$ Km [26]. The temperature at the beginning of the outer core is $T_I \sim 2800$ K, and the temperature at the outer core-mantle is $T_O \sim 2000$ K [10, 16], the conductivity $\sigma \sim 10^4$ S/m [9]. Assuming that the liquid outer core has a metallic behavior with a density $\rho \sim 7 \times 10^3$ Kg/m³ [16, 27], then we may evaluate the Fermi's energy $\varepsilon_F \sim 1.10^{-17}$ Joule. Note: the corresponding Fermi's temperature, $T_F = \varepsilon_F/k_B \sim 10^5$ K, amply justifies our assumption of a degenerate Fermi gas. Using the parameter values, we obtain the thermal magnetic field scale inside the planet

$$B_T = \mu_0 \sigma \frac{k_B T_c}{e \varepsilon_F} k_B \Delta T \sim 0.035 \text{ Gauss.} \quad (8)$$

With sufficient accuracy, the magnetic field generated inside the planet is modeled as a dipole field. We infer that the dipole field decreases as R^{-3} , with R the distance from the source, allowing us to estimate the corresponding surface field. Consequently, we may write:

$$B_S \sim B_T (R_I/R_P)^3 \sim 0.0025 \text{ Gauss,} \quad (9)$$

where B_S is the surface field. Its magnitude is in agreement with the measured field.

Following the planet order, after Earth, we come to Jupiter and its moon Ganymede, which were explored in the 2000s by the Juno and Galileo spacecrafts. Following the approach presented in this paper, the theoretical magnitude of the magnetic field of the two celestial bodies has been evaluated in Ref.[22]. We briefly sketch Jupiter according to new data available. For the temperature of the metallic hydrogen at the beginning of the region extends for a fraction, ranging from 0.6 to 0.8 [17, 28, 29] times the Jupiter radius, we have $T \sim 10000$ K and $T \sim 8400$ K respectively [29, 30]. The density of the metallic hydrogen present in the outer core has a density of $\rho \sim 4 \times 10^3$ Kg/m³ [3, 6]. This allows us to evaluate the Fermi energy, $\varepsilon_F \sim 10^{-17}$ Joule. Finally, a recent estimation of the electrical conductivity gives the value $\sigma \sim 5 \times 10^6$ S/m [31]. Using the parameter values, we obtain the thermal magnetic field scale inside the planet

$$B_T = \mu_0 \sigma \frac{k_B T_c}{e \varepsilon_F} k_B \Delta T \sim 119 \text{ Gauss.} \quad (10)$$

and corresponding to a surface field

$$B_S \sim B_T (R_I/R_P)^3 \sim 26 \text{ Gauss.} \quad (11)$$

We now apply the same considerations to Saturn, which was explored for two decades by the Cassini spacecraft [8, 14]. Using the data given in [14] and references therein, we have a magnetic field at the surface $0.2 \lesssim B_S \lesssim 0.5$ Gauss, a planet radius of $R_P \sim 60000$ Km, an inner core radius of $R_I \sim 15000$ Km, and an outer core radius of $R_O \sim 30000$ Km.

The metallic hydrogen region extends for a fraction, ranging from 0.6 to 0.75 times the planet radius [14]. The temperature at the beginning of the conductive metallic region is $T_I \sim 6000$ K, and the temperature at the outer core-mantle boundary is $T_O \sim 3000$ K [11]. The conductivity of Saturn is of the order of 10^5 S/m [14], while the density of the metallic hydrogen present in the outer core is $\rho \sim 4 \times 10^3$ Kg/m³ [3, 6]. This allows us to evaluate the Fermi energy, $\varepsilon_F \sim 10^{-17}$ Joule. The corresponding Fermi's temperature, $T_F = \varepsilon_F/k_B \sim 7 \times 10^5$ K, again amply justifies our zero temperature Fermi statistics assumption. Using the parameter values, we obtain the thermal magnetic field scale inside the planet

$$B_T = \mu_0 \sigma \frac{k_B T_c}{e \varepsilon_F} k_B \Delta T \sim 2.7 \text{ Gauss}, \quad (12)$$

where we used the intermediate value $\sigma \sim 5 \times 10^5$ for the conductivity, and corresponding to a surface field

$$B_S \sim B_T (R_I/R_P)^3 \sim 0.6 \text{ Gauss}. \quad (13)$$

We now apply the same considerations to the planets Uranus and Neptune. Although the data obtained from the recent spatial missions, the models of Uranus and Neptune interiors are poorly understood and still affected by high uncertainty (see [5, 12, 13, 32] for reviews). It is widely accepted that Uranus and Neptune are rich in water or water-like components and heavy elements, though the specific concentrations vary significantly depending on the model. Several studies propose models in which the interiors of these planets include a layer of metallic fluid hydrogen, considered to be the primary driver of their planetary dynamo. However, it is beyond the scope of this brief report to analyze the various hypotheses in detail. For our analysis, we rely on the model presented in Ref. [7]. In particular, we emphasize that our conjecture about the contribution of the Seebeck current to the planetary magnetic field requires only the presence of a fluid with high electrical conductivity to validate our approximation based on the ideal degenerate Fermi gas. In other words, the presence of a conducting fluid is essential, but it does not necessarily need to be metallic fluid hydrogen.

For what concerns Eq. (7), the two planets' physical parameters have similar values. There is a common agreement that $\sigma \sim 10^5$ S/m. Such a region is modeled to exist in cores out to $\sim 0.9R_P$, while the magnetic field is thought to be generated at $\sim 0.5 - 0.7R_P$ with a temperature at the beginning of the outer core of $T_I \sim 3000$, while the temperature at the outer core-mantle boundary is $T_O \sim 1500$ K. Finally the density is $\rho \sim 10^3$ Kg/m³ [4, 7] giving the Fermi's energy $\varepsilon_F \sim 4 \times 10^{-18}$ Joule. The corresponding Fermi's temperature, $T_F = \varepsilon_F/k_B \sim 3 \times 10^5$ K, amply justifies our assumption. Inside the planets, we have

$$B_T = \mu_0 \sigma \frac{k_B T_c}{e \varepsilon_F} k_B \Delta T \sim 1.62 \text{ Gauss}, \quad (14)$$

where we used the intermediate value $R_I \sim 0.6R_P$ and corresponding to a surface field

$$B_S \sim B_T(R_I/R_P)^3 \sim 0.35 \text{ Gauss.} \quad (15)$$

The results of our discussion are summarized in Table 1, containing all the relevant physical parameters of the planets, and Table 2, where we compare the observed values of the magnetic field and the values given by the thermal contribution.

The data reported in Table 2 are consistent with the conjecture presented in this paper. The assumption of a thermal current density generated by the Seebeck effect, resulting from a thermal gradient between the inner and outer core of a planet, demonstrates its capability to encompass a relevant part of the magnitude of the planetary magnetic field. The presence of a thermal gradient and the essential condition that the degenerate Fermi gas approximation is a well-founded hypothesis for describing the conducting fluid behavior in the planet form the basis of our discussion. This novel approach offers a new perspective for discussing magnetic fields generated by planets.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, we developed our conjecture that thermal density currents (Seebeck effect) can significantly contribute to the magnetic fields of celestial bodies, specifically the planets of our solar system. However, our analysis does not extend to Mars or Venus because Mars' magnetic field is considered a fossil magnetic field, and our knowledge of the interiors of Venus is limited. We evaluated the thermal contribution of the magnetic field using the magnitude scale $B_T = \mu_0 \sigma k_B^2 T_c \Delta T / (e \varepsilon_F)$ for Mercury, Earth, Jupiter (and Ganymede), Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. The results are presented in Table 2, where we compare our findings with magnetic field measurements from various spatial missions, demonstrating a consistent agreement with the observed values.

While we did not face the challenge of solving the magnetohydrodynamic equations, we focused on the magnitude order of the magnetic field and the physic associated. An important feature of the magnetic scaling in our conjecture is its relation with the Fermi-Dirac statistic, which we applied to the fluid of the outer cores of the planets. Our research shows that a thermal current density generated by the Seebeck effect can significantly contribute to the intensity of the planetary magnetic field.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

All authors equally contributed to the work and approved it for publication.

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Data Availability Statement

All data generated or analyzed during this study are included in this published article.

Figure captions

Figure 1: Typical interior of planets. This structure is common to both rocky and gaseous planets. The inner core radius is denoted by R_I , and the temperature at the beginning of the outer core is T_I . The outer core radius is R_O , and the temperature at the outer core-mantle boundary is T_O .

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Planet	R_I	R_O	T_I	T_O	T_F	Liquid outer core
Mercury	10^3Km	$2 \times 10^3\text{Km}$	$2.8 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$2 \times 10^3\text{K}$	10^5K	Liquid Fe, Fe-S
Earth	10^3Km	$3 \times 10^3\text{Km}$	$8 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$4 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$1.4 \times 10^5\text{K}$	Liquid Iron
Jupiter	$4.3 \times 10^3\text{Km}$	$5.7 \times 10^3\text{Km}$	10^4K	$8.4 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$7 \times 10^5\text{K}$	Metallic Hydrogen
Saturn	$3.6 \times 10^4\text{Km}$	$4.5 \times 10^4\text{Km}$	$6 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$3 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$7 \times 10^5\text{K}$	Metallic Hydrogen
Uranus	$1.5 \times 10^4\text{Km}$	$2.3 \times 10^4\text{Km}$	$3 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$1.5 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$3 \times 10^5\text{K}$	Water, Conducting fluid
Neptune	$1.5 \times 10^4\text{Km}$	$2 \times 10^4\text{Km}$	$2.8 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$2 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$3 \times 10^5\text{K}$	Water, Conducting fluid
Satellite	R_I	R_O	T_I	T_O	T_F	Liquid outer core
<i>Ganymede</i>	$0.7 \times 10^3\text{Km}$	$1.7 \times 10^3\text{Km}$	$1.7 \times 10^3\text{K}$	$1.9 \times 10^3\text{K}$	10^5K	Liquid Iron

Table 1: Planetary physical parameters (including the satellite Ganymede in italics to stress that it is not a planet) for the evaluation of B_T . In the second column is the inner core radius. In the third, is the outer core radius. In the fourth, the temperature at the beginning of the outer core. In the fifth, the temperature at the outer core-mantle. In the sixth, the Fermi temperature corresponding to the density of the liquid outer core. Finally, in the seventh, the composition of the liquid outer core.

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Planet	OMF	MFTS
Mercury	0.001 ÷ 0.007 Gauss	0.0015 Gauss
Earth	0.2 ÷ 0.5 Gauss	0.20 Gauss
Jupiter	4.0 ÷ 20 Gauss	26 Gauss
Saturn	0.2 ÷ 0.5 Gauss	0.6 Gauss
Uranus	0.2 ÷ 0.5 Gauss	0.35 Gauss
Neptune	0.2 ÷ 0.5 Gauss	0.35 Gauss
Satellite	OMF	MFT
<i>Ganymede</i>	$7.5 \times 10^{-3} \div 1.4 \times 10^{-2}$ Gauss	$2,6 \times 10^{-3} \div 3.2 \times 10^{-2}$ Gauss

Table 2: Comparison between the observed values of the magnetic field and the values given by the thermal contribution. In the second column the Observed Magnetic Field at the surface (OMF) and in the third the Magnetic Field from thermal current at the surface (MFTS), Eq. (7). The values of the Earth and Jupiter magnetic fields, as well as the magnetic field of the Jupiter satellite Ganymede (in italics to stress that it is not a planet), have been evaluated in Ref.[22].

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